

ASSESSMENT OF GEOENVIRONMENT PROTECTION FROM CONTAMINATION UPON MSW DISPOSAL IN PLATFORM AREAS (BY THE EXAMPLE OF THE MOSCOW REGION)

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ABSTRACT: *Municipal solid waste landfills as a powerful source of contamination, endanger geoenvironment, groundwater in particular. Upon solving the interdisciplinary multi-criteria problem of choosing sites for MSW landfills, geological and hydrogeological factors are usually underestimated. The study is aimed at working out the methodology of assessing the geoenvironment favorability for allocation of MSW landfill facilities within ancient geological platforms by the example of the Moscow region, Russia. At the first step of research, the geological cross-section in Moscow area was typified by its ability to provide a natural protective barrier from landfill pollutants, taking into account the fundamental features of ancient platform geology: weak ruggedness of relief, subhorizontal platform mantle strata, predominantly stratal groundwater aquifers, and significantly different conditions of the formation of pre-Quaternary and Quaternary deposits. The second research step involved ranking the ground massif types according to their favorability for allocation of MSW landfills and performing the special estimative engineering geological zoning and mapping. The resultant map of estimative zoning is aimed at ranking the territory according to the complexity of carrying out waste-management measures and is intended for application upon general multi-criteria assessment of areas in MSW management projects.*

Key words: *MSW disposal, estimative zoning, geoenvironment protection, groundwater contamination*

INTRODUCTION

Disposal of municipal solid waste (MSW) in the geoenvironment and choosing favorable locations for arrangement of landfills appears to be an urgent global problem. The main problems in MSW management are related to the rehabilitation of old landfills, assessment of the possibility of their expansion and further use, and site selection for new landfills. Upon solving this interdisciplinary multi-criteria problem, geological factors are usually underestimated or ignored. However, zoning areas according to the favorability of geological conditions for MSW disposal may give us scientifically grounded idea on the possible safe use of the territory. Such zoning should be based on the basic features of the territory geology (Kozliakova *et al.*, 2020; Osipov *et al.*, 2022; Zaikanov, *et al.* 2018).

Moscow region is located within the ancient East European (Russian) Platform, where a thick Paleozoic-Cenozoic sedimentary mantle covers the Precambrian metamorphic basement (Geology of the USSR, 1971). In the course of its geological history, the platform surface uplifted and subsided, and the marine environment recurrently gave way to a continental one, when ancient river valleys formed on the surface. The longest continental break was registered in the Triassic and Permian periods. A branched network of river valleys of this age is traced on the Carboniferous surface filled with Jurassic alluvium. At the boundary between the Cretaceous and Paleogene periods, the sea retreated from the Russian platform, and a continental break began, which is lasting now. This break is specified by the two main features, i.e., several stages of continental glaciation and the formation of preglacial river valleys. After the last glacier had retreat (about 130 thousand years ago), the entire surface was covered by the layer of glacial and fluvio-glacial deposits of up to some tens meters thick, and the modern relief with the valleys of Moscow River and its tributaries was formed. An important role of marine Jurassic clay in the geological structure of Moscow is worth noting. Almost impermeable marine clay divides the rock massif into two water-bearing complexes. The lower complex underlying the marine clay horizon includes several artesian aquifers of potable water confined to Carboniferous and Devonian limestone massifs. The upper complex that occurs above the marine Jurassic clay is confined to the Quaternary and Mesozoic sandy and sandy-loamy deposits. It also encompasses several aquifers, which are, however, usually strongly contaminated. In the areas, where low-permeable moraine loam strata occur, the following aquifers are distinguished: (a) above-moraine unconfined aquifer, and (b) intra-moraine and under-moraine (often confined) aquifers.

Thus, the engineering geological conditions of Central Russia show all features typical for ancient platforms. They are as follows: weakly rugged relief, subhorizontal or slightly dipping sedimentary layers of the platform mantle, the presence of groundwater of predominantly stratal type, and significantly different conditions of the formation of pre-Quaternary and Quaternary deposits. As proved by many researchers, the study of engineering geological conditions is one of the most important steps in the procedure of site selection for MSW disposal (Balogun-Adeleye *et al.*, 2019; Ghobadi *et al.*, 2017; Djokanović *et al.*, 2020; Schueler, de, 2011; Yuganova, 2019). Those geological structures that provide natural protection of the environment from surface pollution can be considered favorable for waste disposal. The presence of geological barriers, i.e., low permeable clay strata continuous along the strike and occurring close to the surface, is the necessary favorability condition. In Moscow region, the geoenvironment protection is mainly ensured by the presence of persistent by strike and thickness low-permeable strata of preQuaternary (midJurassic clay) and Quaternary (glacial moraine) age. So, this study is aimed at working out the methodology of assessing the geoenvironment favorability for allocation of MSW landfill facilities within ancient geological platforms by the example of the Moscow region, Russia.

TIPIFICATION OF SOIL AND ROCK STRATA IN THE MOSCOW AREA

The first stage of assessing the area favorability for allocation of MSW landfill facilities is typification of the ground massifs in the Moscow region. The ground massifs are typified in order to assess the natural protection of the geological environment from pollution coming from the surface. This protection depends on the presence of low-permeable clayey strata in the geological massif, as well as their number and thickness (Kozliakova *et al.*, 2020). One thick and continuous along the strike layer of Jurassic clay is found among the pre-Quaternary sediments on the territory of the Moscow region, which is considered to be the regional aquiclude. Depending on the presence or absence of this clay layer, two main types of preQuaternary rock massifs are distinguished (Table 1):

I-Carboniferous limestones, sometimes overlain by Jurassic sands (usually aquiferous);

II - Carboniferous limestones, overlain by Jurassic sands and clays, over which Cretaceous sand occurs somewhere (Jurassic clays separate the Carboniferous aquifer from that in Jurassic and Cretaceous sands).

In the Quaternary massif, the weakly permeable layers are represented by moraine loams. There are two moraine layers consistent along the strike, i.e., the Moscow and the more ancient Don moraines. The following kinds of ground massif structures are distinguished depending on their occurrence in the geological cross-section:

1 - Moscow and Don moraines (either both or one of them) occur either on the surface or are covered with thin (less than 10 m) sand layer;

2 - alluvial, lacustrine and fluvioglacial sands and sandy-clayey deposits more than 10 m thick are underlain by moraine loams;

3 - alluvial, lacustrine and fluvioglacial sands and sandy-clayey sediments make up the entire Quaternary sequence; moraine loams continuous along the strike and permanent in thickness are absent in the section.

Depending on the combination of Quaternary and pre-Quaternary massifs, six types of geological structures can be distinguished (Table 1, Fig. 1). The massifs with absent or thin layers (no more than 1 m) of Quaternary deposits are distinguished as separate types (I-I, II-II). The generalized lithological columns were built for all ground massif types showing layers of different water permeability to a depth of about 50m.

The next methodological step consists in the creation of two cartographic informational layers: the spatial distribution of the distinguished types of pre-Quaternary and Quaternary deposits, respectively. Mutual superposition of the two layers resulted in the map of engineering geological zoning, which shows a distribution pattern of various ground massif types in the study area and allows us to judge about the spatial changes in the geoenvironment protection (Figure 1). The map was built for a key site in the north of Moscow region.

Figure 1. The map of typological engineering geological zoning of the key site in Moscow region (Dmitrov town and its vicinities). See Table 1 for designations.

Next we may rank the ground massif types according to the categories of favorability for allocation of MSW landfills and perform the special estimative engineering geological zoning.

Table 1. The principal types of geological structure in Moscow region

PreQuaternary deposits	Carboniferous terrigenous-carbonate deposits somewhere covered by Jurassic sand (usually aquiferous)	Carboniferous terrigenous-carbonate deposits covered by Jurassic clay and sand, over which somewhere Cretaceous sand occurs (Jurassic clay layer separates the Carboniferous aquifer from that in Jurassic and Cretaceous sands)
Quaternary deposits	I	II
Moscow and Don moraines (either both or one of them) occur on the surface or are overlain by sand of low thickness (less than 10 m) 1	I-1	II-1
Alluvial, lacustrine and fluvio-glacial sands and sandy-clayey deposits of more than 10 m thick are underlain by moraine loams 2	I-2	II-1
Alluvial, lacustrine and fluvio-glacial sands and sandy-clayey deposits compose the entire Quaternary massif; persistent by strike and thickness moraine loam layer is absent in the geological cross-section 3	I-3	II-3
Quaternary deposits are absent or their thickness is less than 1 m	I-I	II-II

MAP OF ESTIMATIVE ENGINEERING GEOLOGICAL ZONING OF THE MOSCOW REGION FOR MSW DISPOSAL FAVORABILITY

The estimative zoning of the Moscow region for the disposal of MSW is aimed at ranking the territory according to the complexity of carrying out waste-management measures. The zoning is intended to warn the relevant authorities and companies about the problems they may face when placing landfills in a particular area rather than to put on prohibitions. All ground massifs identified upon typification were classified as favorable, conventionally favorable and unfavorable categories in terms of MSW disposal (Table 2). **The favorable category** is typical for the areas where low-permeable strata occur at the surface preventing penetration of pollutants into the Quaternary and Carboniferous aquifers. Therefore, the geological environment may be considered to be naturally protected from pollution in these areas. **The conventionally favorable category** encloses the areas where a thick, highly permeable sand layer occurs at the surface. In these areas, the geological cross-section contains a low-permeable layer, occurring, however, rather deeply, and thus, protecting only the aquifer in Carboniferous terrigenous-carbonate rocks from contamination. **The unfavorable category** includes the areas, within which there are no low permeable strata of moraine loams or Jurassic clays consistent along the strike. In these zones, the geological cross-section is represented by Quaternary sands and carbonate-terrigenous rocks of Carboniferous age to a depth of 50 m.

Typification and zoning of the region took into consideration the geological structure variability corresponding to the regional level of research. That means that the favorability category may be changed upon performing local large-scale studies and updating geological structure. The spatial distribution of territories showing different favorability categories is shown on the Map of the estimative engineering geological zoning for the allocation of MSW landfills, which gives us an idea of the possible difficulties when disposing of waste in a particular area (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. The map of estimative engineering geological zoning for the key site of Moscow region (Dmitrov town and its vicinities). See Table 2 for designations.

Thus obtained cartographic assessment of territory favorability for MSW disposal, in our opinion, looks easy and understandable. It may be used in the general multi-criterial assessment as an individual informational layer. At the same time, the proposed typification of geoenvironment makes allowance for the main specific features of the geological structure in the considered area.

Table 2. Ranking the Moscow region territory by the favorability degree for the MSW disposal

Favorability degree of engineering geological conditions	Specific features of engineering geological conditions
Favorable I-1, II-1, II-II	One or two low-permeable rock strata are found in the geological massif, which occur almost at the surface.
Conventionally favorable I-2, II-2, II-3	Quaternary sand of large thickness, highly permeable and often water-bearing occur at the surface. The Carboniferous aquifer is separated from the Quaternary aquifer with low permeable Jurassic aquiclude and/or Quaternary moraine. The Quaternary aquifer is not protected from contamination penetrating from the surface. Under these circumstances, the special design solutions should be applied for the construction of MSW disposal facilities.
Unfavorable I-3, I-I	Only highly permeable and water-bearing Quaternary sand and/or Carboniferous terrigenous-carbonate deposits are found in the geological cross-section. The geological environment is almost unprotected from contamination within the bulk of area of this type. The detailed large-scale studies may reveal sites, where clay layers of sufficient thickness occur in the Carboniferous deposits. This may form grounds for upgrading favorability category for a particular site.

CONCLUSION

In the geological structure of the Moscow region, two stratigraphic complexes are clearly distinguished, i.e., pre-Quaternary and Quaternary complexes. They differ in the composition and structure of composing deposits, mode of their occurrence and groundwater content. These differences result from different environments of the formation of these complexes in the sedimentary mantle of the ancient platform. Pre-Quaternary sediments were formed mainly in the marine environment; their composition is terrigenous and carbonate-terrigenous, and their bedding sequence is preserved within sufficiently vast areas. These deposits can they be partially or completely eroded only in areas of ancient river valleys. Quaternary deposits are of continental origin. They are much more variable by strike and in thickness. These are mainly non-lithified or weakly lithified deposits represented by sands, sandy loams and loams. Quaternary aquifer complexes show direct interconnection between the constituent aquifers, which are discontinuous along the strike. Upon special geological mapping of platform territories, Quaternary and pre-Quaternary deposits are shown on separate maps, which makes it possible to obtain a more detailed description of the geological structure of the territory. Analysis of these maps, taking into account the known patterns of geological strata, allowed us to identify typical geological sections in the territory. Proceeding from the presence of low-permeable aquicludes, each geological cross-section type was assessed as favorable, conventionally favorable, or unfavorable for MSW disposal. The spatial distribution of typical sections for different favorability categories is shown on the map of estimative zoning. Thus, the proposed technique for compiling the assessment map is based on taking into account the basic patterns of the geological structure of platform territories. At the same time, it is not too overloaded with information, which is often the case with engineering geological zoning.

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